

Two Aramaic Mortuary Stelae from Nerab

also known as “Nerab 1 (KAI 225) and Nerab 2 (KAI 226)”

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Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

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Nerab 1 (N1) and Nerab 2 (N2) are two seventh century BCE basalt mortuary stelae that were accidentally discovered in Nerab, Syria in 1891. Both contain conventional pictorial reliefs and funerary inscriptions (KAI 225 and KAI 226, respectively). N1 shows in relief a solitary male figure standing in profile facing to the right, with his right hand raised in familiar posture of blessing. The inscription identifies this figure as Sin-zer-ibini, priest (kmr) of the moon god Sahar at Nerab. N2 also depicts a priest of the same deity, but the scene is of two figures, one seated at a food-laden table. The figure is identified as Si'gabbar and holds a cup up to his mouth with his right hand. The second (smaller) male figure is unidentified and stands next to the table in a posture of blessing. The first eight lines of N1 wrap around and the other six run across the legs Sin-zer-ibini. In contrast, the inscription of N2 is distinguished from the iconographic relief. The ten-line inscription is incised on the flat surface of the stele above the scene. Both funerary inscriptions are typical of like inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian period in the region. Not least of all because they invoke typical blessing and curse formulae to ensure their graves would not be disturbed. Moreover, they name the deceased and identify them with the “image” (šlm). They warn against removing the monument under penalty of divine punishment. Both texts invoke the same deities (Sahar, Nikkal, and Nusku), but N1 also invokes the sun god Shamash. There are other slight differences between the inscriptions that are notable. N1 is written in the third person, whereas N2 is in the first person—Si'gabbar speaks directly to the audience. Moreover, Si'gabbar speaks of his experience of death (and speaks after death!), whereas Sin-zer-ibini does not speak for himself. He simply “is dead” (mt). N1 and N2 are two examples of beliefs about the dead in ancient West Asia. Specifically, how care for the dead could incur blessing and destruction of grave sites could invite divine punishment.

Date Range: 700 BCE - 700 BCE

Region: Nerab (Al-Nayrab), Syria

Region tags: Syria

Ancient Aramean city.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Donner, Herbert, and Wolfgang Röllig. *Kanaanäische und aramäische Inschriften: Band 1. erweiterte und überarbeitete Auflage*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2002.
- Source 2: Hallo, William H., ed. *Monumental Inscriptions from the Biblical World*. Vol. 2 of *The Context of Scripture*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.
- Source 1: Boyd, Samuel L. "The Nerab Stelae (KAI 225 and 226)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden/Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://cal.huc.edu/getbibsigla.php?myauthor=Nerab%20Stelae>
 - Source 1 Description: The Comprehensive Aramaic Lexicon provides a rolling bibliography for resources regarding the Nerab stelae. For further study, consult this bibliography.
 - Source 2 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>
- Notes: Boyd, Samuel L. "The Nerab Stelae (KAI 225 and 226)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden/Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

- Chisel

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Notes: Basalt

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Iconographic scene was carved first.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The stelae were accidentally discovered in 1891 when local workers were repairing a hilltop terrace. The stelae were not found in situ, in a controlled, scientific excavation. It is unknown exactly (in their context) where they were displayed or how.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above comment.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Note above.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: In all likelihood, these stelae were privately funded, or funded by the temple. Though, making a hard distinction between the priesthood and the ruling elite is problematic.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The audience would have been anyone who attended the graves of Sin-zer-ibani and Si'-gabbar

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscriptions may have been read aloud.

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: In N1, blessing is incurred (Inn. 12-14)

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: See note above.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: On the basis of comparative evidence, there would have been a set of rituals performed for the dead at the gravesite including feasting. See Herrmann and Schloen 2014

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably as many as were in attendance to visit the dead.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably alcohol would be involved in libation rituals.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– No

Notes: In ancient West Asia and Egypt, the act of writing and the presence of a text can have its own potency and magical efficacy.

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

Notes: In ancient West Asia and Egypt, writing often takes on an apotropaic function. Amulets are incised with writing for protection, homes are inscribed for protection, etc. In the case of N2, the writing literally covers the depicted person. The writing wraps the image of the deceased as a form of protection in death. See Mandell 2022 and Boyd's forthcoming work in PAW.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– Yes

Notes: In some respects this is true of N1 and N2. The use of curse language (and blessing in N1) and its formulation function as an incantation.

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– No

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The manipulation of the stelae, as both N1 and N2 state, will result in divine punishment and death.

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: Carved reliefs.

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– No

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: The stelae are the only extant texts.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: There is no self-evident "collection" of funerary inscriptions in the region. Inscriptions of this kind are lumped together by scholars or by the fact that they are discovered in a cemetery/graveyard/necropolis.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: There is no literary tradition other than that these inscriptions are two of many Northwest Semitic funerary inscriptions.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: There is nothing of the sort. Curses and blessings are present, as are the mention of several deities (Shamash [only N1], Nikkal, Nusku, and Sahar).

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: This sort of distinction is anachronistic for ancient West Asia. Their ontology, to use another anachronism, is quite different from the dualism of Western philosophy and Judeo-Christian theology. In the texts, the image is equated with the identity of the priests, but this does not suggest a dualism as much as a fluid ontology. For example, see Porter 2014.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: In N2, there is explicit reference that Si'-gabbar is not left with goods.

↳ Personal effects?

– Yes

Notes: Si'-gabbar in N2 states that he is only buried in his clothes (lbš).

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Multiple deities: Sahar, Nikkal, Nusku, and Shamash (only NT). Notably, though, both priests serve the same god, Sahar at Nerab. The moon god in Syria was particularly popular, not least the moon god at Harran.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Si'-Gabbar speaks about being dead, but also speaking "my mouth was not closed from words."

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: Si'-gabbar sees only his family and descendants to the fourth generation.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified. Presumably not though.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: Si'-gabbar is able to see into the future and see his descendants.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

Notes: In N1, Sin-zer-ibini will reward those who guard his grave.

↳ Human spirits can punish

– No

Notes: In N1 and N2, the deities deliver punishment, not the deceased.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified. Though this was certainly a possibility in ancient West Asian thinking.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Notes: Apparently the case for Si'-gabbar in N2 at least.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– I don't know

Notes: This is apparently what Si'-gabbar means in N2 when he says, "my mouth was not closed from words." But this is specifically in reference to the day he died.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: The organization is, at the very least, based on the piety of the priests. In both N1 and N2, Sahar is invoked first in the list of deities. Nikkal and Nusku are in the same order as well. On the gods of the Arameans, see Niehr 2014; Lipiński 2000.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Sahar is a moon god; Shamash a sun god; Nusku a fire god; Nikkal is associated with the moon god, at times a daughter of Sin, the Mesopotamian equivalent of Sahar.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Unspecified.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

Notes: Yes, deities are invoked to protect the mortuary stele.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The deities in N1 and N2 care about the proper care of the mortuary stelae. If it is mistreated (removed) they punish the perpetrator.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Not specified.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: In N1 Sahar, Shamash, Nikkal, and Nusku; in N2, Sahar, Nikkal, and Nusku.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is threatened so that others do not desecrate/remove the monuments.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Notes: If death constitutes bad luck.

↳ Other?

–Specify: Death befalls the perpetrator and their descendants.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Only in N1 is blessing mentioned and it is given by the deceased, Sin-zer-ibini

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Proper care for deceased and gravesites.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Protection of the monument.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: If this includes the protection of the monument.

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– I don't know

Notes: This is certainly implied given the context of ancestral veneration in ancient West Asia, but it is not specified in this text per se. See van der Toorn 2017.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Protection of mortuary monuments is emphasized.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– I don't know

Notes: This is not explicit in the texts. However, there are rituals associated with the dead in ancient West Asia, including feasting with the dead. So, this is perhaps implied by the wider context (explicit in other monuments), but not explicitly stated.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– No

Notes: The action is not required, but in N1, if the space is protected, blessing is conferred.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Nothing.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Artisans. Though the deceased priests probably had a say in the content of the inscription.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Two Aramaic Mortuary Stelae from Nerab, Herrmann, Virginia Rimmer, and J. David Schloen, eds.. In *Remembrance of Me: Feasting with the Dead in the Ancient Middle East*. Edited by Virginia Rimmer Herrmann and J. David Schloen. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, 2014.

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